

Yuan divination schools

also known as “Yuan yinyang schools”

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Although some divination students were recorded in Dunhuang’s prefectural schools in the 10th century, it was in Yuan China that local divination schools were established by imperial order for the first time. From 1291 onward, Yuan rulers ordered the establishment of divination schools in various administrative units of the Yuan, from the route down to the subprefecture. Modeled on Confucian schools and medical schools, divination schools were headed by one or more divination instructors, selected for their expertise in divination. The highest ranked ones (9b) were appointed by the Directorates of Astronomy (sitiantai 司天臺) of the central bureaucracy while the lower-ranked ones were recommended by the locals. The Yuan divination school had multiple functions. First, they taught the three fundamental topics of divination (sanyuan 三元), namely geomancy of residence spaces (zhaiyuan 宅元), geomancy of burial site (yingyuan 塋元), and marriage divination (hunyuán 婚元). Second, they managed local diviners, organizing them for local services such as timekeeping. Third, they recommended qualified candidates to the Directorates of Astronomy, which had many activities related to various divination practices. Although not as systematically established as Confucian and medical schools (I have identified 150 divination schools according to the existence of school buildings or instructors), the divination school continued well into the Ming and the Qing periods. The institution’s connection to the Yuan divination households is not always clear. In some cases, the local divination school managed registered local divination households, while in other cases, the divination instructors did not necessarily come from a divination household. Some Yuan divination school instructors published books on the three fundamental topics of divination or on other divination practices, while others networked with local elites, prognosticating for them or writing stone inscriptions, etc. The establishment of local divination schools institutionalized the significance of the three fundamental topics of divination, in particular geomancy. It also strengthened divination instructors’ social status, making divination an alternative profession for traditional Confucian families.

Date Range: 1291 CE - 1368 CE

Region: Divination schools in Yuan China

Region tags: China

Divination schools were established throughout Yuan China except for Tibet.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: *Yuandianzhang* (元典章), annotated by Chen Gaohua (陳高華) et al. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju; Tianjin: Tianjin guji chubanshe, 2011.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://hanchi.ihp.sinica.edu.tw/ihpc/hanjiquery?@29^88387503^802^30202023@@1822463890#top>

– Source 1 Description: 元史 The Dynastic History of the Yuan

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://library.harvard.edu/digital-collections>

- Source 1 Description: Local gazetteers of the Yuan and later periods include information on divination schools, or names of divination instructors. Harvard-Yenching Library has a partial digitised collection of local gazetteers. Set 1
- Source 2 URL: https://hollis.harvard.edu/primo-explore/search?query=Isr38,exact,Harvard-Yenching%20Library%20Chinese%20Local%20Gazetteers%20Digitization%20Project-%20Shan%20ben%20fang%20zhi,AND&tab=books&search_scope=default_scope&sortby=rank&vid=HVD2&mode=advanced
- Source 2 Description: Local gazetteers of the Yuan and later periods include information on divination schools, or names of divination instructors. Harvard-Yenching Library has a partial digitised collection of local gazetteers. Set 2

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: While not a religious group, the divination instructors interacted with local Buddhists, Confucian scholars, and probably Daoists as well.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Assigned by proven expertise in divination.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: New divination instructors were recruited by the state.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: In theory the divination schools were sponsored by the state. But in reality they were frequently sponsored by local governors or local elites.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 300

Notes: In the 1330s, there were 73 divination instructors of the highest rank (9b). 300 is a very rough guess based on this number and the number of divination schools I have found (150).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Notes: The divination instructors were not a religious group per se, but they were a group defined by their expertise in divination.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Divination schools very likely had textbooks, known as the classics of the three fundamentals.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Local gazetteers do not specify the structure of divination school buildings. Confucian schools and medical schools had statues of Confucius and the three medical progenitors, and also served as ritual places.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: The divination content mainly concerned geomancy, the selection or manipulation of locations that balanced yin and yang, hence guarantee the family's good fortune.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Deceased ancestors' spirits were certainly important in the geomancy context.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Grave good can be found in divination instructors' graves. They are usually indications for the instructors' social status and are not necessarily related to their profession.

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In the geomancy context, the surroundings, whether plants, water or stones, could potentially influence the future. In this sense, these were natural beings possessing supernatural powers.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No

 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The natural environment could be manipulated to influence the present and the future.

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Food:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred space(s):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - No
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: the balance between yin and yang

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: They had positive or negative influences on the present and the future.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– No

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: These were norms regarding the living space, the burial site, and marriage.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

–Hours: 360

Notes: As Confucian schools and medical schools had gatherings for both learning discussions and rituals twice a month, divination schools very likely had similar practices.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– No

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

–Yes [specify]: state qualification of expertise

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

— Other [specify in comments]

Notes: a bureaucratic and educational institution

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

— No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

— No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

— No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

— Yes

Notes: One of the major functions of the schools was to provide education in divination to talented young men.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

— No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

— No

Notes: Males only.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: For higher level divination instructor appointments the Central Secretariat and the Directorate of Astronomy was involved.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Like other schools, some divination schools may have school fields.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In accordance with their registered households, divination instructors may enjoy some tax

reduction and exemption from labor and military service.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Yuan state regulated diviners' activities and rules of their bureaucratic transfer and promotion.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: As was the case with other schools, some divination schools may have their own fields, which provided food and income for the school.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Yuan divination schools, Gaohua 陳高華, Chen 陳. "Yuandaide Difangguanxue" (元代的地方官學, the Local State Schools in Yuan China)". In *Yuanshiyanjiu Xinlun* (元史研究新論, New Perspectives on the History of Yuan). Shanghai: Shanghai shehuikexueyuan chubanshe, 2005.

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